

SOP Title	Processing of stool samples and rectal swabs for TRACS-Liverpool study		
Version	3	SOP reference	TRACS_SOP_005
Written By	Esther Picton-Barlow	Date	13/07/2023
Reviewed By	Claudia McKeown	Date	19/08/2024
Authorised By		Date	

Table of Contents

Introduction.....	2
1. Purpose	2
2. Responsibilities.....	2
3. Definitions and Abbreviations.....	2
4. Related Documents.....	3
5. Risk Assessment.....	3
6. Sample Collection/Workflow	4
6.1 Study outline.....	4
6.2 Laboratory sample plan	5
6.3 Receiving samples into the laboratory	6
7. Procedure	6
7.1 Equipment and Reagents.....	6
7.1.1 Equipment required	6
7.1.2 Consumables required	6
7.1.3 Reagents required	7
7.1.4 Reagent preparation and storage	7
7.2 Initial considerations in the laboratory	8
7.3 Sample Processing.....	9
7.3.1 Stool and Rectal Swab Processing.....	9
7.3.2 Selective agar plate processing.....	9
7.3.3 Boiling and qPCR for species confirmation.....	10
11. Review History.....	13

Introduction

The TRACS-Liverpool (Tracking AMR Across Care Settings in Liverpool) study aims to track transmission of extended-spectrum beta lactamase and carbapenemase-producing Enterobacterales (ESBL-E/CPE) in hospitals and care homes in Liverpool. We will do this by recruiting care home and hospital patients and collecting stool and associated environmental samples over a period of months. By testing these samples for ESBL-E/CPE organisms and using gene sequencing techniques to track bacteria we hope to identify where transmission of resistant bacteria is happening. We then aim to combine this information with routine data on antibiotic usage and patterns of care and will work with the hospital flow teams and participating care homes to co-design and pilot interventions to block transmission and, ultimately, reduce the number of drug-resistant infections.

1. Purpose

This document outlines the laboratory methods that will be used to process stool samples and rectal swabs received into the laboratory from the TRACS-Liverpool study.

2. Responsibilities

- Collection team
 - Consent patients and collect samples according to relevant SOPs
 - Correct labelling of collection samples
 - Transfer of swabs to LSTM laboratory

- Laboratory staff
 - Receive samples from collection team and complete sample collection log
 - Processing of swabs in accordance with this SOP
 - Storage of samples for further analysis in accordance with this SOP

3. Definitions and Abbreviations

TRACS	Tracking AMR Across Care Settings
LSTM	Liverpool School of Tropical Medicine
ESBL-E	Extended Spectrum Beta Lactamase-producing Enterobacterales
CPE	Carbapenemase-producing Enterobacterales
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic Acid
CL2	Containment Level 2
MSC	Microbiological Safety Cabinet
BPW	Buffered Peptone Water
TSB	Tryptic Soy Broth
SCAi	Simmons Citrate Agar supplemented with myo-inositol
EcCAB	<i>E. coli</i> Chromogenic Agar B
mLGA	Membrane Lactose Glucuronide Agar
qPCR	Quantitative Real Time PCR

4. Related Documents

TRACS_SOP_003	Stool swab sampling
Risk Assessment for Work with Hazardous Biological Agent_TRACS	Biological risk assessment
Risk Assessment for Use of MALDI-TOF Biotyper	MALDI_RA_01
SOP for MALDI-TOF Users.	MALDI_SOP_001

5. Risk Assessment

<i>Hazard (Cause and Consequence)</i>	<i>Affected Groups</i>	<i>Existing controls (e.g., PPE...)</i>
<i>Biological Hazards</i>		
Stool samples and rectal swabs: potential infection	Laboratory staff and clinical staff	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PPE (lab coat and gloves) to avoid any contact with the body. • All the processing carried out in a Class II MSC. • Any centrifugation steps use aerosol-sealed lid/bucket. • No use of needles/sharps during the sample processing to prevent injuries. • Laboratory workers are monitored by Occupational Health. • Refer to biological risk assessment for further information.
<i>Chemical Hazards</i>		
Virkon Powder: irritant to eyes, skin and corrosive to metal.	Laboratory staff	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PPE (lab coat and gloves) to avoid any contact with the body. Safety glasses should be used when working outside Class II MSC. • Concentration to be used: 2% (no less than 1% final concentration when diluted).
Chemgene: corrosive, irritant to eyes and skin.	Laboratory staff	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Handled in a chemical fume hood with the usage of PPE when in high concentrations. • Once diluted it can be used to spray surfaces. • Final concentration to be used: 5%
<i>Physical Hazards</i>		
None	N/A	N/A

*Refer to MALDI_RA_01 (Risk Assessment for Use of MALDI-TOF Biotyper)

6. Sample Collection/Workflow

6.1 Study outline

To detect the presence of ESBL/CPE-E bacteria in stool and rectal swab samples by an initial enrichment step followed by selective agar plating. Currently, only samples that are positive for ESBL growth will be initially carried forward for sequencing. All samples will be stored to allow follow-up of CPE-E bacteria at a later date.

6.2 Laboratory sample plan

Figure 1 shows the workflow for stool and rectal swab samples.

6.3 Receiving samples into the laboratory

Use Redcap software to receive samples into laboratory. Prepare relevant labels for each sample:

Labels required:

- Enrichment broth tube
- Cryovial for enrichment broth
- Selective agar plate (x2)

7. Procedure

7.1 Equipment and Reagents

7.1.1 Equipment required

Class II MSC	Autoclave
Scissors	Microcentrifuge
Fume hood	37°C Incubator (shaking and static)
Thermomixer	QuantStudio5
MALDI-TOF Biotyper	

7.1.2 Consumables required

Materials	Company/Code
15ml falcon tubes	Fisher/352096/352095
Cryovials	Greiner/122263
Microbank Tubes	Pro-lab diagnostics/PL/160
Cryoboxes	Starlab/A9623-8181 or Simport T314-281B
2ml microcentrifuge tubes	Fisher/3453
1000µl pipette tips (960)	Starlab/S1122-1830
200µl pipette tips (960)	Starlab/S1120-8810
20µl pipette tips (960)	Starlab/S1123-1810
10µl pipette tips (960)	Starlab/S1121-3810
Sterile filter units	Fisher/10229090
5ml serological pipette	Greiner/606180
10ml serological pipette	Greiner/607180
25ml serological pipette	Greiner/760180
50ml serological pipette	Greiner/768180
Stirrer bar	SLS/STI4194
1ul loops	Greiner/731165
Petri dishes	Greiner/632181
Deep well 96 well plate	Greiner/780271
Breathable plate seals	Merck/Z380059-1PAK
0.2ml PCR plates	Starlab/I1402-9700
0.2ml PCR tube strips and caps	Starlab/I1402-3500/I1400-0900
Foil plate seals	VWR/AB0626
qPCR plates	Fisher/N8010560
qPCR plate seals	Fisher/N8010560

7.1.3 Reagents required

Reagents	Company/Code
Sterile Buffered Peptone water	Oxoid/CM1049
Sterile Tryptic Soy Broth	BD/211825
<i>E. coli</i> ChromoSelect Agar B	Merck/70722
Simmons Citrate Agar	Oxoid/CM155B
Myo-Inositol	Merck/I5125-100g
Membrane Lactose Glucuronide Agar	Oxoid/CM1031B
Maltodextrin	Merck/419699-100g
Trehalose dihydrate	Merck/90210-50g
Cefotaxime	Santa Cruz/SC-202989B
PBS	Fisher/ 10010023
Glycerol	Merck/17904
70% Ethanol Solution	Collect from CTID facilities
5% Chemgene Solution	XTM309
2% Virkon Solution	330002
Luna qPCR mastermix	NEB/E3004
Nuclease free water	Fisher/ AM9937
Primers and probes	See section 7.3.3

- Refer to MALDI_SOP_001 for all reagents and equipment if choosing this option for species identification.

7.1.4 Reagent preparation and storage

Preparation of Sterile Buffered Peptone Water (BPW)

- Add 20g of BPW powder to 1 litre of distilled water.
- Mix well and sterilise by autoclaving at 121°C for 15 minutes.
- Store at room temperature for up to 1 month.
- Aliquot 5ml into 15ml falcon tubes in preparation for sample receipt.

Preparation of sterile Tryptic Soy Broth (TSB)

- Add 30g of TSB powder to 1 litre of distilled water.
- Mix well and sterilise by autoclaving at 121°C for 15 minutes.

Preparation of stool solution

- Remove 50ml of PBS from a 500ml bottle.
- Add 9.4g of maltodextrin and 3.1g of trehalose.
- Put into a waterbath set to 40°C until dissolved.
- Add 50ml glycerol (to give a final concentration of 10% glycerol).
- Filter sterilise.
- Add 500µL to each cryovial, aliquoted vials can be stored at room temperature for up to 6 months. 2 cryovials will be needed for each sample.

Preparation of cefotaxime stock solution

- Dissolve cefotaxime powder in water to 200mg/ml.
- Dilute this to 10mg/ml in water to make working stock solution.
- Store at -20°C

Preparation of E. coli Chromoselect Agar B (EcCAB) (plus selection)

- Suspend 36.6g in 1 litre distilled water.
- Mix well and sterilise by autoclaving at 121°C for 15 minutes.
- Cool to 50°C and add cefotaxime to a final concentration of 1µg/ml.
- Pour into sterile petri dishes and store at 4°C for up to 1 month.

Preparation of Simmons Citrate Agar with myo-inositol (SCAi) agar for Klebsiella spp detection (plus selection)

- Suspend 20.7g of the Simmons Citrate agar in 900 ml of distilled water.
- Mix well and sterilise by autoclaving at 121°C for 15 minutes.
- Weigh 10 g of myo-inositol and dissolve in 100 ml of sterile water.
- Cool to agar 50°C and add 100ml myo-inositol solution.
- Add cefotaxime to a final concentration of 1µg/ml.
- Pour into sterile petri dishes and store at 4°C for up to 1 month.

Preparation of Membrane Lactose Glucuronide Agar (mLGA) agar for E. coli detection (plus selection)

- Suspend 88g in 1 litre of distilled water.
- Mix well and sterilise by autoclaving at 121°C for 15 minutes.
- Cool to agar 50°C.
- Add cefotaxime to a final concentration of 1µg/ml.
- Pour into sterile petri dishes and store at 4°C for up to 1 month.

7.2 Initial considerations in the laboratory

- All the samples should be treated as potentially infectious. Therefore, samples must only be opened in a class II MSC until considered inactivated.
- The use of lidded, aerosol-tight centrifuge buckets is compulsory, until otherwise stated.
- Before starting, thoroughly clean the class II MSC with Chemgene (5% solution) and 70% ethanol. Switch the Class II MSC on and leave it running until airflow is safe
- For inactivation of liquid waste or to clean up small spills, use freshly prepared 2% Virkon solution in a 1:1 dilution with waste (no less than 1% Virkon final concentration). For waste containers, leave the Virkon for a minimum of one hour, ideally overnight, before diluting and disposing down the laboratory sink.
- All other solid waste is considered contaminated and must be disposed of by autoclaving followed by incineration.

7.3 Sample Processing

7.3.1 Stool and Rectal Swab Processing

Sample processing should take place as soon as possible, ideally within 24 hours of receipt into the laboratory. Work in a Class II MSC wearing lab coat and gloves. Store samples at 4°C until processing can begin.

Depending on reagent availability, either EcCAB or mLGA agar can be used for *E. coli* detection. Record which agar has been used in TRACS sample spreadsheet.

-
-
1. Scan samples into TRACS sample spreadsheet using TRACS ID QR code on sample tubes. Print labels for sample cryovials, BPW enrichment broth, agar plates and BPW cryovials.
 2. **Swabs:** Transfer the rectal swab into a labelled 15mL falcon tube containing 5mL of BPW enrichment broth. Cut the end of the swab and replace the cap of the falcon tube.
Stool samples: weigh stool sample pot (use an empty pot to zero the balance) and resuspend in sample in stool solution. Use 5x the volume of stool solution per g of stool (e.g. 0.5g stool = 2.5ml of stool solution). Add a small stirrer bar to the pot and place on a magnetic stirrer to agitate the sample. Vortex sample to resuspend if necessary. Add 100µl of resuspended stool into a labelled 15mL falcon tube containing 5mL of BPW enrichment broth.
 3. Incubate the tubes at 37°C, shaking at 220rpm for 4 hours.
 4. Transfer the remaining unprocessed stool sample (up to 5x 1ml aliquots)/rectal swab into pre-prepared cryovials containing stool solution and store in a labelled box at -80°C. Record position in box in ProCuro and ULT freezer layout.
 5. After 4 hours, transfer samples to the Class II MSC and streak each sample out onto 1x EcCAB/mLGA and SCAi agar supplemented with 1µg/ml cefotaxime using a 1µl loop.
 6. Transfer 500µl of remaining BPW enrichment broth into pre-prepared cryovial containing 500µl stool solution and store in labelled box at -80°C. Record position in box in ULT freezer layout.
 7. Incubate the plates overnight at 37°C.
 8. Store falcon tubes at 4°C.

7.3.2 Selective agar plate processing

Following incubation, evaluate plate growth, any growth on EcCAB and SCAi agar is a potential ESBL producer.

-
-
1. No growth: record result and discard plate and corresponding enrichment broth tube.

2. Growth: Interpret plates according to the table below and record the results in TRACS sample spreadsheet. Print qPCR plate layout and labels for plate sweeps.

Agar	Species indication	Colony colour	Example image
mLGA	<i>E. coli</i>	Green, Blue, Yellow	
SCAi	<i>Klebsiella spp</i>	Yellow	
EccAB	<i>E. coli</i>	Blue	

Can progress with either qPCR identification or MALDI-TOF identification.

7.3.2.1 qPCR identification

- Pick a single colony of each positive morphology into a deep well 96 well plate containing 1ml of TSB supplemented with 1mg/ml cefotaxime per well. (If there are only a small number of potential positive samples, 15ml falcon tubes containing 1ml of TSB supplemented with 1mg/ml cefotaxime may be used instead.)
- Seal the plate with a breathable seal and incubate for 4 hours at 37°C, 220rpm.
- Where there are any colonies remaining, or plates with growth but negative in morphology, sweep the plate into a microbank vial using a 10ml loop, shake to distribute and place in the **plate sweep** storage box. Record position in box in ULT freezer layout and store at -80°C.
- Following the 4-hour incubation of the deep well plate, transfer 100µl of TSB into a 0.2ml PCR tube/plate and perform qPCR as outlined below in section 7.3.3.
- Place remaining TSB culture (in the deep-well plate or falcon tubes) back into the incubator at 37°C and shaking at 220rpm. Cultures will be further incubated until qPCR run has finished, or after 3 hours, whichever comes first.

f. qPCR Results:

Export qPCR results as an excel file and copy CT values into TRACS sample spreadsheet. Print biobanking, lysis buffer and DNA labels for positive samples.

Positive for *E. coli* or *K. pneumoniae* on qPCR

- I. Transfer remaining TSB culture into two microcentrifuge tubes (~450ml in each). Centrifuge at 10,000 rpm for 3 minutes and discard the supernatant. Wash pellet with 500ml of sterile PBS and repeat centrifugation step (10,000 rpm, 3 minutes).
- II. **Biobanking:** Discard the supernatant and resuspend the pellet in a 100ml of microbank tube solution, and transfer to a labelled microbank tube. Store at -80°C and record box position in ULT freezer layout.
- III. **DNA extraction:** Discard the supernatant and resuspend the pellet in 300ml lysis buffer from the MasterPure DNA extraction kit. Store at -80°C until extraction can be performed (TRACS_SOP_006). Record position in box in ULT freezer layout.

Negative for *E. coli* or *K. pneumoniae* on qPCR: no further action, record result on TRACS sample spreadsheet and discard sample.

7.3.2.2 MALDI-TOF Identification

- a. Restreak one positive colony on MLGA agar supplemented with 1mg/ml cefotaxime using a 1ml loop.
- b. Where there are any colonies remaining, or plates with growth but negative in morphology, sweep the plate into a microbank vial using a 10ml loop, shake to distribute and place in the **plate sweep** storage box. Record position in box in ULT freezer layout and store at -80°C.
- c. Incubate the plates overnight at 37°C.
- d. Using this fresh plate, that has not been in the fridge, proceed with the SOP for species identification in MALDI SOP 001.

NB: Training is required for the MALDI-TOF use.

Positive for *E. coli* or *K. pneumoniae* on MALDI

- I. Sweep the restreaked plate with a 10ml loop and mix in with 500ml PBS. Repeat in second 500ml PBS. Centrifuge at 10,000 rpm for 3 minutes and discard the supernatant.
- II. **Biobanking:** Discard the supernatant and resuspend the pellet in a 100ml of microbank tube solution, and transfer to a labelled microbank tube. Store at -80°C and record box position in ULT freezer layout.
- III. **DNA extraction:** Discard the supernatant and resuspend the pellet in 300ml lysis buffer from the MasterPure DNA extraction kit. Store at -80°C until extraction can be performed (TRACS_SOP_006). Record position in box in ULT freezer layout.

Negative for *E. coli* or *K. pneumoniae* on MALDI no further action, record result on TRACS sample spreadsheet and discard sample.

7.3.3 Boiling and qPCR for species confirmation

Primers and probes

Name	Target species	Accession Number	Sequence
meth Forward	<i>E. coli</i>	WCT47116.1	CGTGGTGGTCGCTTTTACCACAGAT
meth Reverse			TCCACTTTGCTGCTCACACTTGCTC
meth Probe			[FAM]AAATCTGGGTTRAGCGTGT[BHQ1]
recA Forward	<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	WCN69223.1	CGCGCACTTTCTTCTCAATC
recA Reverse			AGCTACAACGGCGACAAA
recA Probe			[VIC]CGGGTTCTCTTTTCAGCCAGGTGAT[BHQ1]

Before starting: set the thermomixer to 95°C. Thaw qPCR reagents: mastermix, primers and probes – keep on ice until needed.

Thaw positive control DNA: NCTC 13341 (*E. coli*) and NCTC 13368 (*K. pneumoniae*).

- Following from step d. in section 7.3.2: transfer 100µl of cultured TSB into a 0.2ml PCR plate or tube. Centrifuge the plate at 4000rpm for 15 minutes or tubes at 10,000rpm for 3 minutes.
- Carefully discard the supernatant and resuspend the pellets in 100µl of nuclease free water.
- Place the plates/tubes onto a heat block set to 95°C and incubate for 15 minutes to lyse the bacteria. Place the plate on ice once incubation has finished.
- Prepare primer-probe mix as outlined below (prepare 10% excess for the number of samples to be tested + 2 x water negative controls and 2 x positive controls):

Reagent	1x reaction (µl)	Calculation (x number of wells required) (µl)
Luna mastermix	10	
meth Forward	0.8	
meth Reverse	0.8	
meth Probe	0.4	
recA Forward	0.8	
recA Reverse	0.8	
recA Probe	0.4	
Nuclease Free Water	1	

- Aliquot 15µl of prepared primer-probe mix to each well of a qPCR plate. Wells H9-H12 should be used for the positive and negative controls.
- Add 5µl of 4ng/µl of positive controls to wells H9 and H10: NCTC 13341 (*E. coli*) and NCTC 13368 (*K. pneumoniae*).
- Add 5µl of nuclease free water (negative control) to wells H11 and H12.
- Add 5µl of the boilate to each sample well A1-H8 according to plate layout generated on TRACS sample spreadsheet.
- Seal plate with qPCR MicroAmp seal.

10. Open QuantStudio file: TRACS_qPCR_template and upload sample sheet from TRACS sample spreadsheet.

11. Run qPCR as below:

<i>Cycle step</i>	<i>Temperature (°C)</i>	<i>Time (s)</i>	<i>N° of cycles</i>
Initial denaturation	95	60	1
Denaturation	95	15	40
Extension	60	30	

8. Following the run, check positive and negative wells before determining positive samples. If controls fail, qPCR step must be repeated. Ct cut-off for a positive result = 30. Record Ct values in TRACS sample spreadsheet.

Borderline results (Ct 30-31) can either be repeated using full DNA extraction protocol (TRACS_SOP_006) or sent for 16s sequencing (TRACS_SOP_007). Record results in RedCap and return to 7.3.2 section e. to continue processing.

12. Review History

18/07/2023: Changes made to reflect sample recording and label printing in TRACS sample spreadsheet. More colony types included for mLGA agar 'positives'. Additional detail to stool processing step (7.3.1.2).

19/08/2024: Reviewed and added volume of lysis to add, for clarity. Changed simple laboratory plan in 6.2 to add MALDI option. Added in MALDI-TOF preparation methods.